

Mobile Technology Supporting Algebra and Numeracy skills in a Maths Support Learning Centre

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The mathematical ability of students entering third level education in Ireland has been a cause of concern for some time now. This presentation will introduce an action research project designed to identify the most common mathematical challenges students attending the Maths Support Centre (MSC) at an institute of higher education present with. The paper will explore the effectiveness of a mobile learning application on student engagement and learning. Mobile technology applications remain an underutilised resource within higher education and with an increasing number of students using both smartphones and tablets, this study explores the influence of a specific mathematical mobile application on student learning and engagement. The innovative study will present findings helpful to academic staff teaching mathematics and statistics modules, assisting their planning and teaching approaches. Insights from the research and the use of mobile technology will help create effective resources for the students, which in turn support their mathematical learning experience.

Introduction

The level of mathematical readiness for students entering third level education in Ireland has continued to generate widespread concern both in the academic community and the general public in recent times (e.g. O'Donoghue 2002, Gill et al. 2010). One popular approach to tackle these mathematical issues in third level institutions in Ireland is the setting up of maths support centres (MSC). Lawson et al. (2003) described mathematics support as

“a facility offered to students (not necessarily of mathematics) which is in addition to their regular programme of teaching, lectures, tutorials, seminars, problem classes, personal tutorials, etc.” (p.9).

This study aims to analyse the prevalence of mathematical topics students present with at the Maths Learning centre at an institute of higher education. In identifying the student's mathematics “trouble spots” the study will develop effective supports for a number of these. Initial data collected from the IT Sligo maths support centre indicate that the areas of basic algebra and arithmetic that are causing most difficulty with attending students. The research will make use of technology to help provide the services to assist the students.

The study explores the influence of a mobile application on student engagement and how mobile technologies might be used to support student learning. Mobile learning technologies have been recognised as emerging tools to improve teaching and learning (Traxler 2007). The use of textbooks in class are being challenged by the pace of development of mobile technologies which have increased at a significant pace over the last few years.

“More and more young people are now deeply and permanently technologically enhanced, connected to their peers and the world in ways no generation has ever been before. [...] More and more of what they need is available in their pocket on demand” (Prensky, 2010, p. 2).

In the US, the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (2000) considered technology as

“Technology is essential in teaching and learning mathematics; it influences the mathematics that is taught and enhances students’ learning.” (p. 3).

As documented by Olive et al (2010), it is envisaged that the technologies will also help support the students and improve the way they approach, learn and understand the problematic concepts. There are many potential benefits of using mobile technologies for learning such as facilitating learner-generated contexts, as well as personalising the learning for the student as detailed by Cochrane (2010). Calder et al (2016) describes how the features of mobile technologies enable alternative ways to explain, process, encounter and investigate mathematical concepts. The learner to control the flow of information and choose the amount of mathematical content that they wish to access at any one time. These potential benefits make mobile technology seem an extremely useful tool for the learning and teaching of mathematics. This study will explore the how mobile technologies might be used to support student learning in the centre utilising a highly adaptive mobile application tailored to a student’s skill and maths level.

Maths Support Centre at IT Sligo

This study takes place in the Maths Support Learning Centre (MSC) at Institute of Technology Sligo - a free drop-in centre to support all IT Sligo student’s mathematical needs. Cronin et al. (2015) highlight the extent to which the landscape of maths support centres in higher education institutions in Ireland has changed for the positive since 2008.

The Maths Support Centre at the Institute of Technology, Sligo was set up in 2012 as a special inter-school initiative of the institute with the purpose of supporting students’ mathematics learning across all programmes by providing a dedicated area with supervised access and resources to support students in a relaxed environment. The centre delivers appropriate support services for students on service mathematics courses and addresses the mathematical needs of special groups. The findings of this study will help assist MSC and academic staff members with mathematics and statistics modules to plan, enhance and potentially change their teaching approaches of the highlighted topics.

Mathews et al. described the main aims of the maths support centre as

“to address issues surrounding the transition to university mathematics and to support students’ learning of mathematics and statistics across the wide variety of undergraduate courses that require an understanding of mathematical concepts and techniques.” [15, p. 3]

This MSC opened initially for 2 hours during academic term in semester 1 and 3 hours in semester 2. The centre was proving to be a success and a valuable resource to both struggling

and able students based on feedback received from students who used the centre. However, large increases in the number of students attending the MSC over the previous semesters led to a re-evaluation of opening hours. With the support of the newly appointed Educational Development Manager, Institute management agreed to hire a MSC manager and increase the number of contact hours to 24 hours per semester. This has allowed the MSC to extend the existing mathematics support it currently provides to both incoming and existing students in terms of the drop-in clinics, and expand MSC services to include structured mathematics sessions Monday -Thursday, provide revision sessions close to examination times, and deliver online support tutorials, group tutorials and one to one sessions.

The current restrictions and safety concerns around COVID-19 posed a challenge for the proposed study. IT Sligo's delivery plan for the 2020/21 academic year involves a blend of remote delivery and some on campus delivery but only for activities that require active face-to-face engagement with academic staff. As a result, to mitigate any effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the MSC and on face to face meetings with students, the centre went fully online for the 2020-2021 academic year. Through the booking system on the MSC Moodle page, students can book one to one online sessions or group tutorials with the various maths support tutors. To reduce the impact of COVID-19 on student numbers to the centre, the marketing team at IT Sligo promote the centre through the different college social media platforms. Regular emails are also sent by staff and through the student's union to all students highlighting the opening hours for the MSC and the free online one to one mathematical service offered. All students have access to the MSC Moodle page where they get more information on who to contact, the opening days and times. The MSC is in weekly contact with the maths lecturers at IT Sligo and any student that the lecturer identifies as struggling in their class are also encouraged to seek help and get in contact with the math support centre tutors.

Blutick Maths Application

The maths application chosen for this study is the Blutick maths app (<https://blutick.com/>). It is an AI powered maths teaching platform and works as a reactive AI, by applying a large number of algorithmic tests to what the students input. Based on the student's response it then generates a probabilistic assessment of the best response to any mistake made by the student. The app takes into account a variety of different factors, including the stage of the problem the student is currently at, the question context and the mathematical working itself. Positive feedback is generated and designed to both encourage the student and point them in the right direction. There are many thousands of apps available to help students with their mathematical difficulties. Most however simply mark the students attempt or provide the answer to the problem. The Blutick app has the ability to indicate to students where they made their mistake giving the students a better understanding of the problem at hand. Calder & Campbell (2016) argue that apps that provide instantaneous feedback of this type allow the learner to both experiment and take risks with their learning and knowledge intake.

The app provides learning in small accessible chunks by guiding and teaching the students through the different mathematical concepts with a combination of short video content, fully worked out examples, interactive questions and quizzes. The app also processes and stores the lines of work that students enter into the system. It generates suggestions for these scenarios that initially do not offer the intelligent feedback. These scenarios are then examined, with relevant feedback built into the system, ensuring the app is learning over time. As the student works through the various tasks the app identifies what feedback works best, creating a more effective feedback and teaching tool. According to Kukulska-Hulme (2010), mobile technologies allow the learner to improve their knowledge whenever the need arises, with learning occurring in everyday and more varied environments. The task summary page provides more detailed information on each of the tasks undertaken. The instructor can view the amount of time spent viewing the various videos, the number of questions completed at the different levels, the number of mistakes made, and the number of hints used. Full workings of each question completed by the student is also available together with any feedback offered by the AI instructor. Task summaries also allow the instructor to keep track of the tasks set and the work that the students are completing. The app allows the learner to work at their own pace and repeat the necessary mathematical skills as many times as they wish in order to master the concepts undertaken. Rather than just guessing the solution, the app encourages the students to think about the various steps involved in arriving at the solution. It promotes active learning rather than passive learning.

Figure 1

Shows some screenshots from the Blutick app.

Study Methodology

This study stems from the researchers positionality as a mathematician with over six years’ experience of teaching mathematics online. The researcher is part of the digital champion initiative, a collaboration between GMIT & LYIT (www.digitaled.ie), where he is a

digital champion for the School of Business and Social Sciences mentoring staff on developing blended and online teaching and learning experiences.

IT Sligo students volunteer to be part of the study. Any student, 18 years and older who present themselves to the Maths Support Centre are deemed eligible to take part in the study.

At the beginning of the academic year, students across the college complete a maths diagnostic test to try to identify any weaknesses in their numeracy skills. Lawson et al. (2003) describes diagnostic testing as an effective way to highlighting widespread areas of mathematical weakness. The diagnostic test is accessed using the college virtual learning environment (VLE) platform Moodle in the form of an online quiz. The quiz consists of twenty questions across a number of basic numerical topics with the difficulty level of the questions roughly equivalent to Ordinary Level Junior Certificate Maths. Each student is given instant feedback on completion of the test through a raw mark. As a result, students obtaining less than fifteen out of twenty questions correct are encouraged to attend the MSC to improve the numeracy skills and mathematical competency. Any student that has performed poorly in the maths diagnostic test or have presented themselves to the MSC tutors in need of improving their mathematical skills are invited to participate in the study.

The researcher has reviewed current literature as well as engaging with colleagues running similar maths support centres in other Irish HEI’s to help identify the most appropriate data to capture from the study group and aims to identify the different mathematical topics that the students at IT Sligo present with at the centre.

For this study data has been collected from students who have attended the MSC from AY2018/19 and AY2019/20. Course of study, college year, area of difficulty, how often the student attends the centre were some of the data that was collected from each student visit. This was primarily done to gauge the number of visits per semester, the percentage of visits per year and course of study and the area of difficulty. Data collected during this time period, shows there has been on average 350 students visits each semester, with 125 unique visits. Figure 2 gives an overview of the study and the steps involved in collecting both qualitative and quantitative data.

Figure 2

Mobile technology supporting learning in the MSC study overview

Towards the end of semester one of the 2020/2021 academic year a pilot study was conducted with a group of students to test the Blutick app and identify any difficulties or

questions that the students may have in relation to operating the app. During semester two of AY 2020/21 25 students started to engage with the mobile maths app to complement their learning. Initial student data collected from MSC centre visits highlighted the areas of basic algebra and basic arithmetic that were causing most difficulty with attending students. Approximately 70 tasks in both the areas of algebra and basic arithmetic were set for the students to complete. The topics covered range from working with fractions, percentages, and basic arithmetic skills to simplifying expressions and solving both linear and quadratic equations. Students typically use the app in their own time for one to two hours a week over 12 weeks of semester working through various questions which are supported with short videos and worked examples. Reflective events are held throughout the study to capture student feedback. Detailed and comprehensive quantitative and qualitative data will then be collected which will help inform the way in which the use of a mobile maths app will assist in the students learning. The app allows many ways to view a student's progress and engagement with the app. The mark book element of the app allows detailed information on individual tasks to be collected and allow a deeper understanding on where each student is having difficulty. Each task set for the learner has three levels of difficulty followed by a quiz. The student must get six questions correct in the quiz before the task is marked complete. A smart score is assigned to each task as completed by the learner. The score represents the number of questions that are answered correctly but also considers the degree of understanding of the task by looking at other factors such as skipping questions, making mistakes, and using the hints available. Analysis of these results will help measure the effectiveness of this mathematical mobile application on student learning together with identifying the various trouble spots as the students work through the various tasks assigned. The Mathematics and Technology Attitudes Scale (MTAS) (Pierce et al. 2007) together with focus groups will be used to collect additional data, gauge student's engagement and progression with the app and to identify potential areas of improvement.

The MTAS is a questionnaire with five subscales: affective engagement, behavioural engagement, mathematical confidence, confidence with technology and attitude to using technology for learning mathematics. The focus groups for the first cycle will be held at the end of semester two in 2021 and again at the end of the summer for the group involved in the second cycle of the study. A focus group interview was deemed a most suitable qualitative technique for use in this situation. Denscombe (2007, p.115), states a "focus group consists of a small group of people, usually between six and nine in number, who are brought together by a trained moderator (the researcher) to explore attitudes and perceptions, feelings and ideas about a topic". Accurate records of student visits to the centre during the academic years 2020/21, 2021/22 will be collected and maintained, and the information gleaned will help identify the mathematical issues facing the students with a view of providing unique ways to alleviate them.

Results & Discussion

The initial result from the first 2 action research cycles will be presented. The first cycle or cohort of students are completing 70 tasks in the areas of algebra and basic arithmetic

over a 12-week semester block, May 2021. The second action research cycle will consist of a group of students that partake in the college summer school over a 3-week period towards the end of August 2021.

The results will examine how the students engaged with the app and whether the app assisted the student to master the various concepts undertaken. Feedback from the students will look to identify the positive features of the app from their use of videos, worked examples and the ability to work at their own pace. Data will also help identify both the mathematical difficulties the students encountered and their comprehension of information in the areas of basic algebra and numeracy. Tasks summaries will identify the number of questions completed at the different levels, the number and types of mistakes made together with the number of hints used. The ability to view every line of the student's workings as they complete each task, together with the feedback the system generates, will allow a more detailed understanding of both the key problematic areas and how the students used the application to improve their mathematical ability over time.

Conclusion

This presentation will provide an overview of the action research project on mobile technology supporting algebra and arithmetic skills in a maths support centre at an Irish HEI. The worked examples provided by the mobile application, such as the line by line feedback and short videos, describe underlying concepts in mathematical tasks and help scaffold the students, enabling them work through problems on their own leading developing a deeper understanding. The mobile application programme students are engaging with assist their mathematical comprehension will be presented along with the results from two action research cycles.

One of the biggest challenges is both the recruitment of students to the study and keeping the students on track and engaging with the app during a busy academic semester. The current restrictions and safety concerns around COVID-19 has presented another challenge for the proposed study, even though the MSC was setup to provide online support. Despite the many challenges, mobile learning technologies offer enormous potential to enhance mathematical learning and remain an under used resource in third level education.

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